

POLICY ANALYSIS OF INCREASING INTRA AND INTER RURAL CONNECTIVITY IN INDONESIA

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Abstract

Interregional Connectivity Currently, many policy makers in various countries, especially developing countries, undertake development in their countries tend to distinguish between regions that are considered more advanced and regions that are considered lagging behind. Connectivity problems have been the main obstacle in underdeveloped areas, especially those in rural areas of Subang Regency. The results showed that there are areas whose accessibility is difficult to reach, especially in mountainous areas and other areas in the District, and the connectivity between toll roads, provincial roads, and regencies to villages, is not well connected, so it is still felt. There is an imbalance between rural villages that are close to urban areas and isolated villages. Research recommendations need to take a spatial approach in determining development policies and use a regional approach using a 'regional perspective'. With this regional perspective concept, development between regions is no longer independent but there is connectivity between them.

Keywords: Policy, Connectivity, Rural, Indonesia

Introduction

Interregional Connectivity Currently, many policy makers in various countries, especially developing countries, undertake development in their countries tend to distinguish between regions that are considered more advanced and regions that are considered lagging behind. This can be seen in the conditions of development in urban and rural areas where there is very large imbalance, the condition of infrastructure is one component that can be seen. Economic development has always been concentrated in urban areas that are more developed and better equipped for infrastructure than in rural areas. This condition can be easily observed in Indonesia, where development is still Java-centric in nature (Marzali, 2016).

The creation of connectivity between regions in a country is needed to open up new spaces to unify a country. Inequality in development between regions will no longer be created because development does not focus on certain areas and without discrimination on areas that are considered underdeveloped. The World Bank (2009) states that a spatial approach can be used to determine development policies. Through a spatial way of thinking and using a territorial approach, decision makers can think broadly and use a 'regional perspective'. With this regional perspective concept, development between regions is no longer independent but there is connectivity between them. This connectivity is manifested in the availability of infrastructure that connects regions to one another and minimizes gaps between regions. This development increases and levels development, at least economic development, and reduces the poverty rate of a country. Rigg et al (2009) stated that using spatial dimensions is very important in the economic development of a region because it is easily measurable. Maps can

be used as a tangible (visual) development control tool to make it easier for decision makers to monitor their activities.

The position of the village is very strategic for building a country. This is because the village is at the forefront of problem identification; the needs of the community at the grassroots level to the planning and realization of the goals of the state exist at the village level. The problem is that 60 percent of Indonesia's population lives in villages and the fact shows that the highest dropout rate is in villages. Likewise, health problems, such as children under five with malnutrition and the risk of death in childbirth, are mostly found in villages. It is worsened by the underdevelopment of the village economy which has led to an increase in the country's poverty rate (Kompasdotcom, 2012).

Connectivity problems have been a major obstacle in underdeveloped areas, especially in rural areas of Subang Regency, many of the roads are rocky and potholes, as well as roads that connect with other areas whose condition is badly damaged and cannot be passed by vehicles, this is what makes The economy of rural areas is not developing, continues to be in a lagging condition. In addition, there are areas whose accessibility is difficult to reach, especially in mountainous areas and other areas in the District, as well as connectivity between toll roads, provincial and district roads to villages, not well connected, so there is still a sense of it. Inequality, between rural villages that are close to urban areas and isolated rural villages. Based on the research background and these problems, researchers are interested in conducting research related to Increasing Intra and Inter-Rural Connectivity (Case Study in Subang Regency).

Methods

Development and social problems related to Intra and Inter-Rural Connectivity in Subang District, a research approach is needed that can help researchers to understand the phenomena related to these problems. By looking at the phenomenon being studied about Intra and Inter-Rural Connections in Subang District, it is unique and complicated, so this research uses qualitative methods. The qualitative method aims to understand and interpret the meaning of a phenomenon that occurs, to then be analyzed and attempt to explain the phenomenon with descriptions given by the researcher. Thus, in the end, the researcher can give meaning to the results of the research in depth. In order to support this research method, researchers used the following data collection techniques: 1) Literature Study; 2) Field Study (Observation and Participation, Interview); 3) Focus Group Discussion (FGD) involves stakeholders on the topic of Policy for Increasing Intra and Inter-Rural Connectivity in Subang Regency which is directed at forming a joint agreement or consensus starting with an effort to explore or pour out ideas from several experts according to their fields of expertise as well as technical and theoretical mastery of various the field in question.

In data validation, the researcher made steps for data validation by means of triangulation. Valid if the data obtained is accurate between researchers, participants and other related parties. The triangulation technique used by the author is an examination technique that utilizes the use of various sources, namely observation, interviews, secondary data. The data

validation technique was taken through confirmation of the informants' statements and the documents studied. Meanwhile, to find out the reliability of the research, Yin as cited by Creswell (2009: 190) argues that qualitative researchers need to document the procedures of their studies and to document as many of the steps of the procedures as possible, so that reliability is carried out by documenting all stages. In research. In this study, researchers used data analysis techniques according to Miles and Huberman. This qualitative data analysis can be described as follows:

Figure 1: Qualitative Data Analysis: Matthew B. Miles and A. Michael Huberman's Interactive Model

Source: Miles and Huberman (1992).

According to Matthew B. Miles and A. Michael Huberman (1992), qualitative data analysis is a cyclical and interactive process that moves between four axes, namely data collection, data reduction, data presentation and drawing conclusions or verification.

Results and Discussion

Village and Village Development

The village is an area that has captured the attention of many parties, various problems can be studied and urged to be resolved. The economic power of the village is helpless against the market mechanism, and the village is always in power and imbalance relations with the city. In general, villages in Indonesia face the threat of underdevelopment and injustice in development. Naturally there is a kind of dilemma, namely poverty and low knowledge that cause excessive use of natural resources to survive, but on the other hand there are many resources that have not been utilized optimally, such as sunlight, water, wind, plants, fish, and livestock. And human labor (Daldjoeni&Suyitno, 2004: 126). The same thing was expressed by Rustadi that in the traditional community sector there are many natural resources that have not been developed optimally due to the backwardness of the community, lack of capital, so that the level of productivity is low and has implications for low income levels (ErnanRustadi, 2009: 142). Limited knowledge and capital are factors that hinder village development.

Apart from the aforementioned problems, there are other more important issues, namely the highly sectoral development paradigm. Each agency or ministry has a program to the village according to its affairs, regardless of the territorial dimension and synchronization with other sectors. Tarigan argues that the development program should be a combination of sector approaches and regional approaches (Tarigan, 2008: 43). Lewis stated that the development of a region will stagnate if only one sector is developed (ErnanRustiadi, 2009: 146). This means that the success of development is an effort to integrate various sectors in a particular area. This integration requires integrated management and collaboration between the stakeholders involved. So that building a village is a multi-dimensional process and involves all stakeholders who work together. Village development is a process of responding to the three village environments (natural, cultural and socio-economic) in an appropriate way (Daldjoeni&Suyitno, 2004: 37)

The village government becomes the center of village governance which has relations with the BPD, elements of civil society, and the economic community. The position of the village head is the personification of the village government. The village government and village heads are part of the state bureaucratic chain that carries out regulatory and control functions in the region through administrative services, implementation of development projects, community mobilization to support government policies in providing services to residents in the village. Meanwhile, according to Sunartiningsih (2004) village empowerment in the context of village society is the ability of individuals who are united in society and build the empowerment of the community concerned. A society where most of the members are physically and mentally healthy, educated and strong, of course, has a high level of empowerment. However, apart from physical things like that, intrinsic values such as family values, mutual cooperation, and diversity are also developed. This empowerment then becomes the basic element that allows a society to survive and in a dynamic sense develop itself to achieve its goals. Community empowerment places more emphasis on efforts to increase the dignity of the layers of society who are currently unable to escape from the traps of poverty and underdevelopment. In other words, empowering the community means enabling and independent the community. Widjaja (2011) has explained that the essence of empowerment is an effort to awaken all existing village capabilities to achieve goals. The achievement of goals is carried out through the growth of motivation, initiative and creativity to advance the economy and bring prosperity to the village.

In this context, Intra and Inter-Rural Connectivity in Subang Regency is interpreted as the availability of infrastructure that connects regions to one another and minimizes gaps between regions, efforts made by local residents through the capacity of village government institutions and the emancipation of their citizens to be able to make use of them. the ability, initiative / initiative and village movements collectively (working together) in developing potential sources of regional assets that are owned both physically and non-physically. Various actors are involved in village development both from government institutions, namely the Village Government, village community organizations, economic actors, and even involve cooperation with external parties such as private involvement. With the

development of the village, the goal and hope is that the village is able to become independent and can increase the economic status of the surrounding community.

Intra and inter-rural connectivity

Talking about rural-urban development, it cannot be separated from regional development. This is because villages and cities are two different areas and empirically there is always migration from villages to cities.

Subang Regency is an area whose topography can be classified into three zones, namely mountainous areas with an altitude between 500-1500 meters above sea level and an area of 41,305.09 hectares, undulating areas with an altitude between 50-500 meters above sea level and an area of 71,502.16 hectares, and low land with an altitude between 0-50 masl and an area of 92,639.7 ha. Based on the topography, the climate typology of Subang Regency according to the Schmidt and Ferguson scale consists of a slightly dry, wet, and very wet climate. The average air temperature in Subang Regency is 27 ° C with an average air pressure of 0.01 millibar, 66% sunshine and 80% relative humidity. Annual rainfall ranges from 1,100-3,200 mm / year.

Subang Regency is the administrative area of West Java province which is located at coordinates 107 ° 31 ' - 107 ° 54' East Longitude and 6 ° 11 ' - 6 ° 49' South Latitude with an area of 205,176.95 Ha or 6.34% of the area of West Java Province. (DKP, 2017). Subang Regency consists of 30 sub-districts and 245 villages and 8 sub-districts. Four of the 245 villages are coastal village areas because these villages are located in a coastal area and are the center of fishery sector activities, both capture fisheries and aquaculture. The four villages are Blanakan village, TanjungTiga village, Rawa-meneng village, and Mayangan village.

The coastal village institutional system, especially the one that deals with fishermen's problems, is generally ineffective. Of the 4 coastal villages, only Blanakan Village has an institution with very good and effective management. The fishing institution of the Blanakan Village community is the Mina FajarSidik Village Unit Cooperative (KUD). The good service and the relatively high price of the fish catch causes fishermen from other villages to land their catch in Blanakan Village.

The existence of infrastructure in an area is very important, including the coastal villages in Subang Regency. This is because infrastructure can support people's lives both socially and economically. School infrastructure, especially SD, is found in all coastal villages, junior high schools are in Blanakan and Tanjungtiga villages, while SMA is only in Blanakan Village. The infrastructure is provided by the government and partly by the private sector. Apart from school infrastructure, other types of infrastructure for coastal villages are as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Infrastructure Infrastructure for the coastal village of Subang Regency

No	Physical Infrastructure	Village			
		Blanakan	Tanjungtiga	Rawameneng	Mayangan
1	School	12	5	3	1
2	Puskesmas and other health services	11	10	9	3
3	Rice milling industry	6	19	7	0
4	PDAM	1	1	1	1
5	Transportation (Asphalt road (km))	6	5	3	1
6	Transportation (Bridge)	11	7	9	2
7	Communication means and electronic media	3249	2140	838	1
8	Fish Landing Points	1	1	1	0

Source: BPS Blanakan&Legonkulon District BPS (in Muliani et al, 2018).

The interaction and connectivity of the coastal village areas of Subang Regency are formed through a complex interaction process. In the internal village system, social interactions are formed between resource users and infrastructure providers, ecological interactions are formed between aquatic ecosystems and mangrove ecosystems as well as adaptation and response to environmental changes. The interaction of socio-ecological systems is formed through the interaction between resources and resource users. Meanwhile, external connectivity between villages is built through the social interaction of education and fishing systems from Rawameneng, Tanjungtiga, and Mayangan Villages to the education system and fishermen institutions in Blanakan Village which are then connected in the coastal village social ecological system network, as shown in Figure 2 as follows:

Figure 2: The network of connectivity in the coastal village of Subang Regency.

Source: (Muliani et al, 2018)

The latest development of a theory or concept to reduce intra- and inter-rural regional disparities is the Regional Network Strategy for Reciprocal Rural Urban Linkages developed by Mike Douglass (1998). The strategy expressed describes a regional development strategy that forms a network of urban villages as a unit and has interdependence. The proposed analysis and policy framework is to address the urban village gap, which has been debated in the debate on territorial theory and planning. The strategic framework developed departs from a study in the context of regional development. The findings that must be considered in the reciprocal relationship between rural and urban development are the need for data to harmonize policies in the flow of people, production, commodities, capital, and information as can be seen in Table 2 as follows:

Table 2: Interrelationships and Inter-and Inter-Rural Dependencies (Village - City)

NO	URBAN	↔	RURAL
1	Center for trade / agricultural / fishery transportation	↔	Agricultural / fishery production
2	Agriculture / fisheries support services Production input Repair / repair service Information about various production methods (innovation)	↔	Agricultural Intensification Rural infrastructure Production incentives Training and capacity building efforts to implement and adapt innovations
3	Non-agricultural consumer market Agricultural processed products Private services Public services (health, education, government administration)	↔	Rural demand and income. For non-agricultural goods and services
4	Agriculture / fishery based industry	↔	Seasonal crop production and diversification of agriculture / fisheries
5	Non-agricultural work / business field	↔	All work / business fields as mentioned above

Source: adopted from Douglass, 1998.

Douglass requires that dichotomy in rural and urban development planning should be avoided, it is even better to prioritize collaboration between the two government administrations in charge of rural-urban areas. This collaboration also applies in intra and inter-rural (village-city) spatial planning. Thus, the inter-rural (rural-urban) spatial and inter-rural (rural-urban) spatial functional relationship between the city as a node and the village as the back area is replaced by one that is a partnership network. The consequence of this paradigm shift is the emergence of an alternative concept of regional intra and inter-rural (rural-urban) networks in the form of clusters that emphasize the linkage of intra and inter-rural (rural-urban) transportation infrastructure and facilities.

Conclusion

The creation of connectivity between regions in a country is needed to open up new spaces. The position of the village is very strategic for building a country. The problem of connectivity has been the main obstacle in underdeveloped areas, especially those in rural areas of Subang Regency. Intra and Inter-Rural Connectivity in Subang District is defined as the availability of infrastructure that connects regions to one another and minimizes gaps between regions. The interaction and connectivity of the coastal village area of Subang Regency is formed through a complex interaction process. In the internal village system, social interactions are formed between resource users and infrastructure providers. Meanwhile, external connectivity between villages is built through social interaction of education and fishing systems from the villages of Rawameneng, Tanjungtiga, and Mayangan towards the education system and institutions of fishermen in Blanakan Village which are then connected in the social ecological system network of coastal villages.

The research recommendation, to reduce intra and inter-rural regional disparities is the Regional Network Strategy for Reciprocal Rural Urban Linkages, dichotomy in rural and urban development planning should be avoided, and should even prioritize collaboration between the two government administrations that lead rural-urban areas.

Conflict of Interest

No potential conflict of interest relevant to this article was reported.

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